

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF AVATAR THERAPY FOR REFRACTORY AUDITORY HALLUCINATIONS TO IMPROVE QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH SCHIZOPHRENIA: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Auditory hallucination is one of the positive symptoms of patient with schizophrenia that is often occurred. Apart from pharmacological therapy, these symptoms can be reduced with non-pharmacological treatment such as AVATAR therapy (Audio Visual Assisted Therapy for Refractory Auditory Hallucinations). This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of AVATAR therapy for refractory auditory hallucinations to improve quality of life in patients with schizophrenia. Articles were searched through Pubmed, Ebsco, Scopus, and Science Direct databases with keywords: patients with schizophrenia, AVATAR Therapy, quality of life. There were seven selected articles. AVATAR therapy is effective in reducing the frequency, intensity, and distress impact of auditory hallucinations. The study results showed that AVATAR therapy provided significant clinical benefits, including improving patients' quality of life and ability to manage hallucinatory symptoms. Additionally, this therapy is well accepted by patients and shows a high rate of completion of treatment. Overall, AVATAR therapy offers an innovative approach to treating persistent auditory hallucinations, especially in patients who do not respond optimally to conventional treatment. Implementation of this therapy in clinical practice requires further research to optimize its benefits and increase its accessibility.

Keywords: AVATAR therapy, Auditory Hallucination, Patients, Quality of Life, Schizophrenia.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hallucinations are perceptions that occur when a person is awake and feels something without any stimulation from the outside world that corresponds to the relevant senses. Hallucinations are perceptions that occur when a person is awake and feels something without any stimulation from the outside world that corresponds to the relevant senses. Although hallucinations can sometimes be experienced by people who do not have mental disorders, hallucinations are often a symptom of mental disorders, such as schizophrenia. Apart from that, hallucinations can also be caused by the use of certain drugs that affect the mind. Even though they seem similar, these hallucinatory experiences can differ in various aspects, either in the way they appear and their impact on the sufferer (Zmigrod et al, 2016).

One of the most common types of hallucinations is auditory hallucinations. The experience of hearing sounds in the absence of appropriate external stimuli constitutes. It is one of the most disturbing symptoms of psychosis and is difficult to treat with medication. Model Cognition explains that the way a person perceives the sounds they hear, like who they are, the voice, how strong it is, what its intentions are, and whether they feel they can control it, really affects how much pressure they feel and how they respond (Calafell et al, 2015). Birchwood et al (2014) stated that it is not just frequency or content sounds that influence a person's emotions or behavior, but also the nature of an individual's relationships with a personified voice. Based on social ranking theory, they found that individuals who feel powerless or inferior in social relationships tend to experience something similar when interacting with sound.

About 70% of people with schizophrenia experience auditory hallucinations. These sound hallucinations often cause high stress and can affect everyday life, with voice content that often contains threats, commands, or harsh comments. Despite optimal drug treatment, these sounds often persist for years (Turner et al, 2020).

In situations like these, innovative therapies such as AVATAR therapy are starting to attract attention as a potential solution. AVATAR therapy is a computer-based intervention that aims to reduce the frequency and severity of sounds. Even though it's not a complex immersive environment, this therapy uses a Virtual Reality (VR) platform to create and present human or non-human identities to patients. It aims to facilitate real-time voice "dialogues" between participants, and representations computerization of their voices, and therapists (Calafell et al, 2015). AVATAR therapy provides new insights into how interactions between patients, therapists, and sound representation can create significant changes in a patient's life. In the future, a deeper understanding of implementation and mechanisms of therapy will be an important step to improve treatment outcomes in patients with persistent auditory hallucinations. This literature review aims to determine the effectiveness of Audio Visual Assisted Therapy Aid for Refractory Auditory Hallucinations (AVATAR Therapy) to improve quality of life in patients with schizophrenia in Patients with Auditory Hallucinations.

2. METHODOLOGY

This literature review used a literature review study design. The process of the literature search begins by determining keywords through PICO framework analysis, which has been adapted to the MeSH Term. Literature was searched through various databases, including Pubmed, Ebsco, Scopus, and Science Direct. Inclusion criteria: Randomized Controlled Trial, Clinical Trial, Quasi-Experimental, Case Study Year: 2014-2024, English, Free Full Text.

Table 1. PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Output)

Population	Patients with schizophrenia
Intervention	AVATAR Therapy
Comparison	No
Output	Quality of life

Table 2. Key Concept and Mesh Term

	Concept 1	Concept 2	Concept 3
Key Concept	Patients with schizophrenia	AVATAR Therapy	Quality of life
Mesh Term	Patients with schizophrenia Hallucination Hearing hallucination	AVATAR Therapy; Audio Visual Assisted Therapy Aid for Refractory Auditory Hallucinations; Therapy	QoL; Quality of Life;

Table 2. The Number of Articles in Each Database

	PubMed	Ebsco	Scopus	Science direct
Concept 1	848	245	756	4.418
Concept 2	20.994	17.453	9.870	6.301
Concept 3	255.372	18.738	224.675	10.729
Concept 4	6	253	64	2.533
Fit with Criteria	2	43	39	70
Selected	2	2	1	2

Figure 1. Prisma Flowchart

3. RESULTS

There were 7 selected articles that fulfilled criteria. The articles showed that AVATAR therapy was not only feasible and acceptable by participants, but also non adverse events. This therapy uses a three-dimensional model (AVATAR) that represents the hallucinatory sounds experienced by the patient. In therapy sessions, patients interact with the avatar, allowing them to confront and control excruciating hallucinatory experiences. AVATAR therapy provides a listener experience voice is brought into therapy in a new way, allowing face-to-face interaction with a digital representation (avatar) whose speech perfectly matches the tone and intonation sounds that disturb the patient or sounds that the sufferer hears with hearing hallucinations. In rapid development, from initial trials to randomized controlled trials, firstly, AVATAR therapy has shown

great clinical benefits for voice listeners (Craig et al., 2018). By utilizing digital technology to create interaction realistic and controlled therapy, this therapy not only helps reduce symptoms but also empowers patients to well manage their hallucinatory experiences. The findings were obtained if participants participated in all series of AVATAR therapy including meeting sessions and participating in a series of activities, there may be a decrease level of hallucinations in patients.

4. DISCUSSION

AVATAR therapy is a therapy that uses three dimensions in a space simulation displayed on a computer. Avatar therapy usually lasts 50 minutes per session given once a week for six weeks. Before starting therapy, the patient together the therapist creates a computerized simulation or avatar of the desired voice they omitted including what the voice said, how it sounded and how it looks. This therapy is effective in reducing the patient's level of hallucinations at once increase the patient's awareness of reality. This is in line with research by Craig, T. K., et

al (2018) shows that there is an effective influence on the use of avatars for reducing the level of verbal hallucinations. The first session was held in week 1, the second session carried out at week 12 and the third session at week 24. There are main results is the reduction in auditory verbal hallucinations at 12 weeks, measured by the total score at Psychotic Auditory Hallucination Symptom Rating Scale (PSYRATS-AH).

Research conducted by Liang, N., et al (2021) used VR (Virtual Reality) showed a decrease in auditory verbal hallucinations in patients with the disorder psychotic. Avatar therapy is showing initial success in helping patients gain control the verbal hallucinations they experience. Patients will take part in virtual realities (VR) activities for 50 minutes, where the patient will communicate with the avatar, he sees based on the voice he makes listen, the therapist will monitor the avatar from a separate room and ensure the patient has a dialogue with avatars according to the hallucinations they hear.

Research conducted by (Craig et al. *Trials*, 2015) shows preliminary data on this therapy can be an effective tool to reduce the frequency, volume and impact of negative impacts hallucinations heard by the patient. This session consists of seven sessions. Session one is for introductions and sessions two to six for implementation of the avatar intervention. This intervention lasts 45 minutes in each session.

The study "One-Year Randomized Trial Comparing Virtual Reality-Assisted Therapy to Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy for Patients with Treatment-Resistant Schizophrenia" which conducted by Laura Dellazizzo, et al. (2021) which compares VRT and CBT interventions. The results show that both interventions succeeded in providing significant improvements in severity of AVH and depressive symptoms in the short term. However, VRT shows greater superiority over CBT in reducing overall AVH, with a value of Cohen's $d = 1.080$ for VRT compared to $d = 0.555$ for CBT. Additionally, VRT also showed a more positive effect on patients' affective symptoms and quality of life. This improvement lasted up to one year, although there was little in the VRT group decreased engagement with sound from month 3 to month 12. This research too revealed that VRT provides a more individualized approach than CBT, in where direct interaction with a personalized avatar allows participants to feel more involved and empowered in facing their hallucinatory voices.

The study entitled "Status and Clinical Experiences from the Challenge Trial – A Randomized Controlled Trial Investigating Virtual Reality-Based Therapy for Auditory Hallucinations" carried out by Ditte Lammers Vernal, et al. (2023) aims to evaluated the effectiveness of Virtual Reality-Based Therapy (VRT) compared to supportive counseling in overcoming auditory verbal hallucinations in patients with disorders spectrum schizophrenia. The intervention group received Virtual Reality-Based Therapy (VRT) consisting of 7 sessions during the first 12 weeks and 2 additional sessions in 12 weeks next. In VRT, the therapist uses VR software to create an avatar resembles the patient's hallucinatory voices, thereby enabling a therapeutic dialogue between the patient and the patient that voice. This approach aims to help patients face, control and reduce the impact of sound experienced. On the other hand, the control group received support counseling, namely standard care usually given to psychotic patients in outpatient clinics road. Preliminary results show that approximately 80% of patients in the intervention group were successful completed 7 therapy sessions, indicating a good level of engagement.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the literature review that has been carried out, there are 7 articles with the AVATAR intervention that can be used to reduce the level of hallucinations in patients. The intervention involves a patient, a therapist and AVATAR. The patient will interact with avatars, allowing them to encounter and control experience hallucinations and be monitored by a therapist. The results of the literature review proved that the 7 articles with this intervention can reduce the level of hallucinations in patients with psychosis problems. Therefore, it is recommended that nurses use this intervention to reduce the level of hallucinations in patients.

Suggestions for nursing practice include considering the use of AVATAR therapy as an intervention to reduce the level of hallucinations. But nurses are necessary receive special training before implementing the treatment to be able to understand this method in depth. Further research needs to be done to explore the effectiveness of this therapy in various cultural contexts and service systems different health.

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